

DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL ACTIVITY OF UNORGANIZED YOUTH: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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Abstract. *This article describes the main directions of State Youth Policy, in particular, the mechanisms for the development of social activity of unorganized youth, the ways of implementation and the work carried out with them.*

Keywords: *youth, state, state, state, unorganized youth, youth problems, solutions, unemployment, quality education.*

Introduction. The implementation of State Youth Policy in Uzbekistan is significant in that it provides an opportunity to tax the work in the field of State Youth Policy in our country, assess the results achieved and the shortcomings allowed, familiarize yourself with the modern mechanisms and methods in this direction. As you know, in 2017 The Youth Union of Uzbekistan was established on President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev's initiative, and the date of June 30 was called "Youth Day" in our country. In addition, a completely new system in the practice of Uzbekistan, that is, a special Institute for the study of youth problems and the training of promising personnel was established, which is engaged in the study of various pressing problems of young people. The establishment of this institution under the state Academy of management under the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan became the basis for the formation of scientific and methodological and analytical research activities of the Institute on the basis of modern requirements.

Research Methodology. As for the concept of "unorganized youth", this phrase is formed from the combination of the words "unorganized" and "youth". The root of the word "unorganized" is "unorganized", which is explained in the Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language in the content of "organized, stable", and the word "association", which is meaningless to it, is "the Union of people or organizations united to act together on the path of one goal." Hence, logically, "unorganized" is the opposite of "unorganized" or "unorganized", meaning antonym, meaning "unorganized, non-stable, unorganized to act together in the path of a particular purpose". Before talking about the development of social activity of unorganized youth, it is important, first of all, to study the self of unorganized youth, their consciousness, behavior, level of socialization, formation, development and upbringing. Unorganized youth is distinguished from the other class of youth by its tendency to commit crimes.

Analysis and results. In order to determine the level of effectiveness of the selected technologies in teaching of the subject of information technology, various methods were used, such as observation, questioning, testing, a written survey, in order to study the effectiveness of students' work on themselves, NPM strives to increase management autonomy by replacing bureaucratic rigidity with marketlike competition. While the specific mechanisms of the NPM approach often seems to be only briefly discussed by researchers and commentators, a review of the literature reveals that practitioners of NPM appear to employ a wide-range of administrative processes that blend public and private resources and processes in the

implementation of public policy, including public-private partnership arrangements and networks, strategic planning and management techniques, outsourcing and privatization of public services, and also nonprofit service delivery organizations.

NPM is a management philosophy used by governments to modernize the public sector and it is based on neoliberalism philosophy which views citizens as a client and provides them various alternatives for choice, it emphasizes to the market model of governance. It believes in 3Es:

- 1) Economy;
- 2) Efficiency;
- 3) Effectiveness

As a result of the survey, the following NPM addresses beneficiaries of public services much like customers. NPM on the other hand seeks to introduce the element of “market orientation” in public administration. Called for rollback of the state and more role for the market. Hence increase competition in the process. Business management strategies and behavior, where public administrators take calculated risks using public resources and employing businesslike strategies (e.g. strategic planning, privatization, public private partnerships, etc.) within a competitive environment, probably generated the most controversy. There is no doubt that the traditional model of public administration played a historic role in the economic transformation in many countries, including Uzbekistan. There are some preconditions for successful implanting the new public management approach. There should a reasonable level of economic development and experience of the operations of the markets, since NPM principles are essentially market-oriented. However, there is a range of factors required before the markets can be effective. A well-developed judicial system is required to provide the rule of law. The new model assumes that the basic administrative processes are in order in the administrative system. They work as a foundation upon which a market-oriented system such as NPM can be implemented. Uzbekistan since independence clearly set a path on economic and social development with the gradual transition to a market economy. They were launched a strong legal basis. There were made major works on privatization and demonopolization of many government structures. Made over the past few years a wide range of measures to promote the consistent way of deepening market reforms and liberalization of the economy, the improvement of the business environment, promote competition, encourage accelerated development of small business and private entrepreneurship, thus fully established preconditions for the full implementation of the NPM principles. As a result, in comparison with 2000, the share of small business in GDP rose from 31 percent to 65 percent, the number of people employed in this sector has increased over this period by more than a factor of 3, and it accounts for more than 76 percent of employed in the economy.

Conclusion. Considering all these collected questions, we think it is necessary to take the necessary measures within the limits of NPM. We have a great potential for new public services in the tourism sector with enhancing innovative technologies, the creation of more public services like opening of new air flight services between the cities, the tourist information center, online ticketing for transportation and more. Services within the rail coaches on a contract basis should be transferred into private enterprises, which will also improve the quality of public services. All these factors will indeed serve to attract more tourists from abroad. Making a conclusion we can say that there are more examples, where applicable the concepts of NPM for Uzbekistan, but we emphasized the main highlights where it’s needed to start using to enhance the value of public

service first. In the course of our analysis, we made a big conclusion and understood that Singapore and Uzbekistan have many similarities in the history of construction of their early statehood. Thus, if the state still actively continues to apply the concepts of NPM to improve public services, and will be fully implemented in the real life, within the next decades we can expect even more significant results in the development of our Uzbekistan. conclusion, this study proves that the use Labster virtual laboratory in education can positively affect the motivation and performance of students. The results show that the use of virtual reality technologies can be used to create an environment conducive to autonomy, which encourages students to take responsibility for their education and actively participate in the learning process.

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